

The Mausoleum of Galla Placidia

Secondary source

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The so-called mausoleum of Galla Placidia was initially an annex chapel of a cross-shaped basilica with aisleless arms, which is known under the name of S. Croce (the Holy Cross). This church was founded between 425 and 450, by Galla Placidia, the daughter of emperor Theodosius I (Theodosius the Great). Nowadays, only the ruins of the S. Croce basilica are preserved. The annex chapel was an oratory dedicated to S. Lorenzo Fomoso. However, it seems that it was intended to host the tomb of Galla Placidia. This never happened because the empress died in Rome and she was buried there. The mausoleum of Galla Placidia is a small building in the shape of a Latin cross with barrel-vaulted arms and a high central bay that supports a pendentive dome. The windows are framed by blind arcades; classical cornices set off the pediments over the arms. The masonry is composed of very high bricks and narrow beds of white mortar. The interior decoration is elaborate and related to the art of the Imperial court. The walls are coated with grey marble down to the floor level. The iconographic program of the monument is simple, composed mainly of various decorative elements and not so many figures. The hemispherical dome and the four pendentives are decorated with the starry dark blue sky and a golden Latin cross in the middle. The longer arm of the cross is turned towards the east. On the four sides, in the sprandles, the four symbols of the Evangelists (the Lion, the Eagle, the Angel and the Ox) appear through clouds. Right below, in the four drums that support the dome, eight Apostles dressed in white tunics are represented in couples. Each couple stands on both sides of a window. Below each window, there is either the representation of a perirrhanterion between two doves or two doves drinking from a basin. The Apostles look up to the sky and with vivid gestures, they glorify the Apocalyptic Cross at the centre of the dome. This scene is inspired by imperial iconography, but it is related to the Last Judgment, which will be announced by the Cross that will appear from the east. The four symbols of the Evangelists are also related to the Apocalyptic Cross because they will surround the Throne of God during the Last Judgment. Thus, the entire scene of the dome is a glorification of the Cross of Salvation, which is the key to eternity. The other four Apostles are represented in couples, among undulating vine leaves, in the vaults of the western and the eastern arms of the chapel's cross. This is probably an allusion to John 15,1-8 'I am the vine; you are the branches. If you remain in me and I in you, you will bear much fruit'. At the key of these two vaults, there is a medallion enclosing the Christogram and the apocalyptic letters A Ω that symbolise the beginning and the end of the world, namely Jesus Christ. The northern and the southern barrel-vaults are decorated with stars, rosaces and tangled tendrils on a blue background, imitating the decoration of textiles. The lunettes of the western and the eastern arm are decorated with two deer drinking water from a small lake lying between them. The rest of the surface is occupied by acanthus branches. This scene symbolises the souls that are thirsty for the divine truth, according to Psalm 41 (42). The scene of the Good Shepherd is depicted in the lunette of the northern arm, above the entrance. The background is light blue. Christ is represented in the middle, sitting on a rock. He wears a golden tunic and a purple mantle. He holds a Latin cross with His left hand, while with His right hand He touches tenderly one of the six sheep that surround Him in the heavenly setting. The fact that this scene is situated above the entrance indicates its connection with the passage from the gospel of John (10,7-10) 'I am the door of the sheep. All that ever came before me are thieves and robbers; but the sheep did not hear them. I am the door; by me if any man enters in, he shall be saved, and shall go in and out, and find pasture.' Thus, it underlines the importance of the entrance, as the gate to the State of God, which is the Church. Furthermore, the Good Shepherd can be linked to the Apocalyptic Cross at the

centre of the dome, as it is a symbol of the triumphant Christ in Paradise, surrounded by the righteous. The scene has been inspired by the representation of Christ-Orpheus surrounded by animals. Opposite the entrance, in the lunette of the southern arm, on a light blue background, there is a man dressed in white, supporting a cross-shaped staff on his right shoulder and holding an open book with his left hand. He is moving quickly from the right to the centre, where there is a burning grill. On the left side is depicted an open bookcase; the four gospels appear on the shelves. Despite the lack of an inscription, it is accepted that this is S. Lorenzo, to whom is dedicated the entire chapel. As a deacon, S. Lorenzo was reading and guarding the gospels; this is why they are in the scene beside the burning grill, which is the instrument of S. Lorenzo's passion. Therefore, this scene conveys the message that the Saint was tortured and became a martyr for the sake of the truth written in the gospels. In terms of style, the mosaics of the so-called Mausoleum of Galla Placidia are attached to the Hellenistic tradition.

Date Range: 425 CE - 450 CE

Region: Ravenna, Mausoleum of Galla Placidia

Region tags: Italy

The so-called Mausoleum of Galla Placidia in Ravenna built between 425 and 450 CE.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Verhoeven, M. 2011. *The Early Christian Monuments of Ravenna: Transformations and Memory*. Turnhour
- Source 2: Jäggi, C. 2016. *Ravenna: Kunst und Kultur einer spätantiken Residenzstadt; die Bauten und Mosaiken des 5. und 6. Jahrhunderts*. Regensburg
- Source 3: Cortesi, G. 1978. *La chiesa di Santa Croce di Ravenna alla luce degli ultimi scavi e ricerche*. *Corso di Cultura sull'Arte Ravennate e Bizantina* 25: 47-76.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.turismo.ra.it/en/culture-and-history/unesco-world-heritage/mausoleum-of-galla-placidia/>
- Source 1 Description: Official Tourist Information Site of Ravenna
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/galla-mausoleum>
- Source 2 Description: The internet site 'The Byzantine Legacy' aims at providing documented, quality information on art, architecture and history from Late Antique, Early Christian and the Byzantine eras.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1970s

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavation in the church of S. Croce in Ravenna

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Small building in the shape of a latin cross.

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Annex chapel of cross-shaped basilica known under the name of S. Croce

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: San Lorenzo Fomoso

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: Galla Placidia, daughter of emperor Theodosius I

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ Good Shepherd

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saint Lorenzo, the Apostles

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Sheeps, birds

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Cross, stars

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Dado

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Symbols of the Evangelists

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Christ Good Shepherd, the Apostles, S. Lorenzo

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Cross

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Sarcophagi

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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